

Table 4 - Number of participants who answered pre and post questionnaires

Question	Pre teaching questionnaire	Post teaching questionnaire
Knowledge of anaphylaxis	98.8% n = 407	83.9% n = 346
Knowledge of AAI	98.8% n = 407	83.5% n = 344
Confidence in recognising anaphylaxis	98.3% n = 405	81.1% n = 334
Confidence in knowing what to do if someone was experiencing anaphylaxis near by	98.3% n = 405	81.3% n = 335
Confidence in using AAI	98.1% n = 404	82.3% n = 339
Was the teaching session the right level of information for you?	NA	82.3% n = 339

n = number of participants who answered the question